

OBSERVATIONS ON THE ENZYME SYSTEM INVOLVED IN THE OXIDATION OF GLUCOSE TO GLUCONIC ACID BY *A. NIGER*

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Aerobic and anaerobic oxidation of glucose by enzyme preparation of *A. niger* in presence of hydrogen acceptor has been investigated. Specificity of the enzyme and the effect of inhibitors on the reaction have also been studied.

Behaviour of the living mould has been studied both under aerobic and anaerobic conditions and in presence of hydrogen acceptors and KCN as inhibitor.

The two component theory of oxidation of glucose in which the enzyme system is supposed to consist of dehydrogenase and a specific glucose oxidase is confirmed and the oxidase is considered to be distinct from cytochrome oxidase.

The production of gluconic acid as a result of microbial activity has long been known. Muller (*Biochem.Z.*, 1928, 199, 136) was the first to make an effort to explain the mechanism of the formation of the acid. He prepared an extract by subjecting a mixture of the mycelium, sand and kieselguhr to a pressure of 300 atmospheres. Muller (*ibid.*, 1929, 205, 111; 1929, 213, 211) further concentrated it by precipitation with 96% alcohol or alcoholic ether mixture. He studied the properties of the preparation and obtained gluconic acid by oxidation of glucose with this extract and according to him the enzyme preparation contained glucose oxidase, different from Warburg's respiratory enzyme. Later on, he (*Naturwiss.*, 1940, 28, 516) found the enzyme preparation to consist of two parts—an oxytropic dehydrogenase and an anoxytropic dehydrogenase, to which 2:4-dichlorophenol-indophenol could act as the hydrogen acceptor. Franke *et al* (*Annalen*, 1937, 532, 1) separated from *A. niger* and *P. glaucum*, an enzyme which functioned as glucose dehydrogenase and oxidised glucose to gluconic acid and was cyanide-insensitive; molecular oxygen and methylene blue could act as hydrogen acceptors. Later, Franke *et al.* (*Annalen*, 1939, 541, 117) discovered glucose oxidase from *A. niger*, *P. glaucum*, and cytomyces. Subsequently he developed a method for its isolation and studied its properties, and termed it a flavin enzyme. Yasuyuki Ogura (*Acta Phytochim. Japan*, 1939, 11, 127) obtained from moulds, grown on synthetic media, an enzyme which he named glucose dehydrogenase. Methylene blue and also molecular oxygen could not act as hydrogen acceptors for the enzyme but thionine, *o*-chlorophenol, quinone etc. could do so.

These dissimilar experimental evidences lead to the conclusion that the formation of gluconic acid is not due to a common principle present in all the strains of the moulds producing gluconic acid. It varies from strain to strain. The exact mechanism involved appears to depend almost solely upon the nature of the strain. Hence in the present investigation, the enzyme of a particular strain has been used. In a system containing a specific glucose dehydrogenase, the evidence to justify the existence of another "glucose oxidase", as postulated by Muller, needs further investigation. Since the apparent specificity of the aerobic function may result from the combined effects of (i) specific glucose dehydrogenase and (ii) non-specific molecular oxygen

activating system e. g., cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase. The effect of KCN upon the gluconic acid fermentation process may also throw light on the problem. The anaerobic formation of gluconic acid in presence of hydrogen acceptors is also another interesting point. It is also equally interesting to enquire how far the synthesis of cells is related to gluconic acid formation. These are a few aspects of the problem which require further elucidation to arrive at the enzymatic mechanism of gluconic acid formation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Four days' old mycelial growth of a strain of *A. niger*, isolated in our laboratory, was used throughout and its metabolic habits were thoroughly investigated (Table I). The strain was grown on glucose medium consisting of glucose (150 g.), KH_2PO_4 (0.6 g.), MgSO_4 (0.5 g.), dibasic ammonium phosphate (1.4 g.), chalk (3.0 g.) and water to make 2000 c.c. at p_n 5.6 and at a temperature of 32° . This medium has been subsequently referred to as the glucose medium. In a typical experiment, the moist mycelium (80 g.) was washed 10 to 12 times into a total volume of 40 lbs of water and finally starved for 6 hours in normal saline in order to remove the remaining traces of glucose from the cell as far as possible. The mycelium was then dried over CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator, wrapped with black paper to exclude light as far as possible. The dried mycelium was powdered and kept as stock in the desiccator under vacuum and away from light. For the day's experiment, a portion of the powder was taken in aqueous suspension to give a concentration of 25 mg. of dry mycelium per c.c.

TABLE I

Metabolic habits of the strain of A. niger.

Conc. of glucose soln. = 3.75 g. in 50 c.c. water. Incubation period = 7 days.
 $p_n = 5.6$. Temp. = 32° .

Metabolites.	Yield of metabolite	Glucose equiv. of metabolites.	
Gluconic acid	2.890 g	2.550 g.	70.65%
Oxalic acid	0.003	0.002	0.04
Citric acid	0.030	0.028	7.75
Carbon dioxide	0.177	0.121	3.23
Mycelium	0.544	0.498	13.27
Unreacted glucose	—	0.280	8.93
Total	3.644	3.559	94.87

This suspension was mechanically shaken and used as the source of enzyme in experiments with Warburg's apparatus. For experiments with the Thunberg tube, the dried mycelium powder was ground up with one third its weight of washed sea-sand in a ground glass mortar mixed with water to give a suspension a strength of 50 mg. of the mycelium per c.c. and shaken for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour mechanically and centrifuged. The centrifugate was used as the source of enzyme in experiments with Thunberg tube, as the use of mycelium suspension as such prevented the accurate judgment of the colour change in the Thunberg tube.

Different substrates were tried including glucose and sodium salt of acids like gluconic, malic, succinic, and pyruvic. The inhibitors tried were KCN, NaF, chlorotone and urethane. The hydrogen acceptors used in the Thunberg tube were methylene blue and 2:6 dichlorophenol-indophenol.

Experiments with the Warburg's apparatus and Thunberg tube.—The aerobic activity of the mycelium suspension was measured manometrically in Warburg's apparatus. Necessary controls were kept in all cases. The composition of the contents of the flasks was as shown in Table II, A.

TABLE II

A. Warburg apparatus.		B. Thunberg tube.	
Mycelium suspension (50 mg./c.c.) ..	0.8 c.c.	Phosphate buffer (pH 6.5) ..	1.0 c.c.
Phosphate buffer (pH 6.5) ..	1.0	Dye soln. (12.5 mg./100 c.c.) ..	0.4
Substrate solution (4.5 M/32) ..	0.4	Substrate (4.5 M/32) ..	0.4
Water or inhibitor (6 mg./c.c.) or dye solution (12.5 mg./100 c.c.)	0.8.	Enzyme soln. (25 mg. of dried mycelium per c.c.)	0.8
		Inhibitor (6 mg./c.c.)	
		or distilled water.	.. 0.4
Total volume ..	3.0 c.c.	Total volume ..	3.0
Temp. ..	37.5°	Temp. ..	37.5°

The anaerobic activity of the extract was measured by Thunberg technique with 2:6-dichlorophenol indophenol and methylene blue as hydrogen acceptors. The composition of the contents of the Thunberg tube was as shown in Table II, B, unless otherwise stated.

Estimation and Identification of Gluconic Acid.—Gluconic acid was identified as the phenylhydrazine derivative and by determining the mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of gluconic acid phenylhydrazone. Gluconic acid was estimated both by macro and micro methods. In the macro method the calcium gluconate formed was estimated via calcium oxalate (May *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1934, 26, 575) and in the micro method gluconic acid formed was estimated directly by titration with standard alkali.

Formation of Gluconic Acid from Glucose by the Dried Mycelium.—The dried mycelium (0.5 g.) was added to 50 c.c. of sterile medium containing the usual nutrients and a few drops of toluene, and the mixture was incubated for 48 hours. The medium was analysed thereafter. An yield as high as 60% of gluconic acid on the basis of glucose taken was reached.

Quantitative Relation between the Glucose used and Gluconic acid formed and Oxygen utilised.—These relations were established with the aid of the Warburg's manometer (Table III); 10.125 mg. of glucose were initially employed.

TABLE III

No. of expt.	Glucose consumed.	Gluconic acid formed.	Oxygen used.	Glucose used on the basis of O ₂ utilised.	Gluconic acid formed on basis of O ₂ utilised.
1.	3.36 mg.	3.70 mg.	0.30 mg.	3.39 mg.	3.68 mg.
2.	2.68	3.12	0.25	2.61	3.06
3.	2.85	3.20	0.26	2.92	3.19
4.	3.05	3.46	0.28	3.16	3.43

The actual and calculated values were well within the limits of experimental error. Thus quantitative conversion of glucose disappearing into gluconic acid confirms the earlier observations of Muller and others made with the strains of *A. niger*. This would indicate that probably all gluconic acid producing strains of *A. niger* have this ability for quantitative conversion.

Specificity of the dried Mycelium.—The enzymic character of the reaction is evidenced by its specificity. The reaction was tried with substrates like fructose, gluconate, oxalate, succinate and malate in the Warburg's apparatus. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Enzyme=50 mg./c.c. In case of glucose as a substrate, only 10 mg. per c.c. were used.

Substrates.	Oxygen absorbed in cm.^3 at N.T.P. during					
	0 min.	15 min.	30 min.	45 min.	60 min.	75 min.
Fructose	0	2	5	7	7	8 c.c.
Gluconate	0	1	3	4	5	5
Oxalate	0	0	2	3	4	5
Succinate	0	3	4	4	5	6
Malate	0	2	4	5	6	7
Glucose	0		45	60	72	86

The results show the specificity of the enzyme system present in the dried mycelium for the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid.

Thermolability of the Preparation.—The preparation of the enzyme was exposed to different constant temperatures for 30 minutes and then its activity measured in terms of oxygen absorption. The results show the thermolability of the enzyme and the thermal death point to be about 72° .

Optimum p_H for the reaction was determined in the usual way. The results show the optimum p_H to be about 6.5. It should be noted in passing that it is a case of optimum p_H range rather than that of optimum p_H .

Anaerobic Experiments.

The anaerobic behaviour of the enzyme extract was studied in Thunberg's tube with glucose as the substrate. Methylene blue and 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol were used as hydrogen acceptors. The intervals after which 40%, 60% and 80% decolorisation took place were determined (cf. Quastel, *Biochem. J.*, 1924, 18, 519). The results were found to be negative with respect to the former dye, and positive to the latter.

Methylene blue was as rapidly reduced with glucose as without it. But the presence of glucose very appreciably diminished the reduction time of the 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol.

Nature of the Dehydrogenation Product of Glucose by dried Mycelium in presence of Hydrogen Acceptor.—To identify the product of this dehydrogenation as gluconic acid

the previous experiment was repeated under anaerobic condition with the medium comprising ingredients normally employed, along with one or other of the hydrogen acceptors like the sodium salts of malic, lactic, and pyruvic acid (*cf.* Wood *et al.* *Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 349). The technique of maintaining the anaerobic condition consisted in conducting the fermentation in small Erlenmeyer flasks which were evacuated inside a desiccator and refilled with nitrogen to a pressure slightly less than that of the atmosphere. The results indicated incapacity of the dried mycelium to oxidise glucose to gluconic acid in complete absence of air, even in presence of hydrogen acceptors tried.

An effort towards this end was again made with the help of the Warburg's manometer using ferricyanide-bicarbonate technique (Quastel *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 936). The results are indicated in Table V.

TABLE V

Glucose dehydrogenating activity by Warburg's manometer.

System.	Oxygen absorbed in mm ³ . at N.T.P. during							
	0 min.	25 min.	50 min.	75 min.	100 min.	125 min.	150 min.	175 min.
Enzyme only	0	8	13	18	24	28	31	35
Boiled enzyme+glucose	0	6	7	10	12	14	16	20
Enzyme+glucose	0	8	12	20	27	34	39	44
Boiled enzyme+glucose+dye	0	7	7	10	13	14	17	21
Enzyme+glucose+dye	0	8	12	20	28	34	40	44

No definite conclusion can be drawn from the above results, but it can be inferred that the dried mycelium did possess glucose dehydrogenating power, although it was not found possible to identify the product of dehydrogenation.

Specificity of the anaerobic behaviour was demonstrated by the inactivity of the preparation towards a number of substances as shown in Table VI A and Table VI B; 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol was used as the hydrogen acceptor.

TABLE VI A

System.	% Decolorisation		
	40%	60% Decolorisation time.	80%
Enzyme only	23 min.	34 min.	45 min.
Enzyme+glucose	11	16	21
Boiled enzyme+glucose	60	—	—
Enzyme+gluconate	32	48	63
Boiled enzyme+gluconate	87	—	—
Enzyme+fructose	22	33	45
Boiled+enzyme+fructose	82	—	—
Enzyme+glycerophosphate	42	60	87
Boiled enzyme+glycerophosphate	90	—	—
Enzyme+lactate	30	55	72
Boiled enzyme+lactate	85	—	—

TABLE VI B

System.	% Decolorisation		
	40%	60%	80%
	Decolorisation time		
Enzyme only	22 min.	34 min	45 min.
Enzyme + succinate	17	28	35
Boiled enzyme + succinate	69	—	—
Enzyme + malate	18	28	36
Boiled enzyme + malate	72	—	—
Enzyme + pyruvate	28	43	57
Boiled enzyme + pyruvate	80	—	—
Enzyme + oxalate	90	—	—
Boiled enzyme + oxalate	94	—	—
Enzyme + glucose	11	16	21
Boiled enzyme + glucose	80	—	—

Both the tubes containing succinate and malate assumed a violet colour and hence the results obtained are not reliable.

The p_H optimum for Anaerobic reaction.—The optimum p_H for the anaerobic reaction was also determined following the usual procedure and was found to be nearly the same as that for the aerobic (p_H 6.5). *Oxygen absorption in presence of 2:6-Dichlorophenol-indophenol.*—Warburg's apparatus was used in the usual way with the suspension of dried mycelium and glucose as substrate with 0.4 c.c. of a solution of 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol (25 mg./c.c.). The results (Table VII) indicate a definite fall in oxygen uptake in presence of the dye. This may be due to the poisoning of the enzymes concerned in the oxidation by the dye.

TABLE VII

Enzyme = 50 mg./c.c. of the suspension.

Rate of oxygen absorption in mm.³ at N.T.P.

No. of expt.	In absence of dye in					In presence of dye in				
	0 min.	10 min.	15 min.	20 min.	25 min.	0 min.	10 min.	15 min.	20 min.	25 min.
1.	0	94.0	132.0	165.6	196.8	0	62.4	88.8	114.0	130.2
2.	0	92.8	130.2	162.8	194.0	0	60.0	93.8	118.4	144.0
3.	0	96.0	138.8	166.0	200.0	0	58.0	90.0	110.8	136.4
4.	0	94.0	127.8	162.0	192.4	0	60.8	87.2	112.0	137.0

Behaviour of the Living Mould under Anaerobic Conditions.

Effect of Anaerobiosis on the Growth of the Strain both in Presence and Absence of Hydrogen Acceptors.—Three Erlenmeyer flasks of 250 c.c. capacity, each containing 50 c.c. of glucose medium which in one case contained one or other of the usual hydrogen acceptors and in another case contained none, were inoculated and incubated for 8 days under an anaerobic condition. After the incubation period was over, the flasks were examined

for growth. The flasks were re-exposed to air and further incubated for a period of 8 days and then analysed. In complete absence of air, no growth of the strain was observed in either cases, but anaerobiosis did not kill the organism at least within 8 days. So re-exposure to air caused growth, accompanied by the formation of gluconic acid (Table VIII A). Absence of growth might be ascribed to the lack of energy required for growth, which in the present case resulted from the aerobic oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid. Hence absence of oxidation caused absence of growth. Moreover, anaerobiosis was found to have an unhealthy effect on the gluconic acid producing ability of the organism as evidenced from the lowering of yields (Table VIII A). It might also be stated that the hydrogen acceptors tried served no useful purpose (Table VIII A)

TABLE VIII A

	Anaerobically exposed strain re-exposed to air.	Control strain.	Anaerobically exposed strain in presence of hydrogen acceptors. re-exposed to air.
% Yield of gluconic acid on basis of glucose taken	69.2	84.3	66.5
% Glucose metabolised	82.4	98.0	83.9
Wt. of mycelial growth (in g.)	0.524	0.532	0.540

Effect of Anaerobiosis on the Aerobic Growth of the Strain in presence of Hydrogen Acceptors.—The strain was incubated aerobically for 4 days to obtain a luxuriant growth of the mycelium, which, after removing the original fermented liquor, was washed aseptically in saline and allowed to ferment for 4 days under anaerobic condition; an equal quantity of a fresh medium of identical composition, except that it contained some hydrogen acceptors in quantity equivalent to theoretically needed amount of oxygen to oxidise glucose taken to gluconic acid. The results are given in Table VIII B. Another set of experiments was carried out exactly in the same way except that the aerobic growth after anaerobic incubation for 4 days was further incubated for 4 days in presence of air. The results are shown in Table VIII B).

TABLE VIII B

Glucose = 3.75g. in 50 c.c. medium.

Hydrogen acceptors used.	Wt. of mycelium from anaerobic expt.	% Yield of gluconic acid $\equiv$ glucose taken under anaerobiosis.	Wt. of mycelium on exposure to air.	% Yield of gluconic acid $\equiv$ glucose taken on exposure to air.
Malate (6.84 g.)	0.50 g.	0.0	0.82 g.	69.2
Lactate (4.66 g.)	0.53	0.0	0.84	70.9
Pyruvate (4.40 g.)	0.51	0.0	0.85	69.6

The data in Table VIII B indicate that even the aerobic growth could not produce gluconic acid anaerobically in presence of hydrogen acceptors tried. Re-exposure to air caused formation of gluconic acid and also the weight of mycelium formed was increased.

It may be stated thus that oxygen is essentially needed for the production of gluconic acid and that the formation of gluconic acid is accompanied by the synthesis of new cells, because the formation of fresh mycelium occurred even in presence of only 4 days' old mycelium for gluconic acid production.

Inhibition Experiments

The effect of inhibitors e. g. KCN, NaF, chloretone and urethane on the anaerobic action of the enzyme preparation upon glucose was studied in Thunberg's tube. None of the inhibitors except chloretone had any effect on the enzyme action (Table IX A). The inhibition experiments were also carried out in the Warburg's manometers with KCN solution concentration of which varied within wide limits and it was observed that the inhibition was not complete, but partial and constant within a wide range of cyanide concentration (of the order of 0.66%) (Table IX B). This inhibition constant, although independent of cyanide concentration, is dependent upon time. Thus with the progress of the reaction, the values of this inhibition constant for different periods, e. g., 10, 20, 30 and 40 minutes were respectively 0.66, 0.67, 0.70 and 0.71. This apparent disagreement in the values of the constant with time might be due to the presence of gluconic acid formed which would complicate the issue still further.

TABLE IX A

Inhibition experiment with Thunberg's tube.

System.	Percentage decolorisation.		
	40%	60%	80%
Enzyme alone	31 min.	46 min.	60 min.
Enzyme+glucose	15	26	35
Enzyme+glucose+KCN	15	26	35
Enzyme+glucose+chloretone	27	39	52
Enzyme+glucose+urethane	15	26	35
Enzyme+glucose+NaF	15	23	30

TABLE IX B

Effect of KCN on oxidation in different concentration

Enzyme = 25 mg. per c.c.

System.	Time in minutes,					
	0	10	20	30	40	50
	(Oxygen absorption in mm. ³ at N.T.P.)					
Enzyme alone	0	1.0	2.0	4.0	5.0	6.0
Enzyme+glucose	0	64.0	99.2	126.6	167.5	176.2
Enzyme+glucose+KCN (2mg./c.c.)	0	54.6	91.4	119.4	149.6	168.4
Enzyme+glucose+KCN (4mg./c.c.)	0	52.0	88.2	115.6	144.8	161.4
Enzyme+glucose+KCN (6mg./c.c.)	0	42.0	66.4	90.2	114.0	122.8
Enzyme+glucose+KCN (8mg./c.c.)	0	43.4	67.0	92.0	115.2	125.0
Enzyme+glucose+KCN (10mg./c.c.)	0	42.2	67.0	90.0	112.6	124.0

These inhibition experiments, as represented in Tables IXA and IXB, indicate that the enzyme system of *A. niger* consists of two distinct enzymes *viz.*, glucose oxidase and glucose dehydrogenase, each of them can function independently.

The inhibitor KCN seems to have no effect on the anaerobic action of the enzyme preparation on glucose (Table IX A), but since in presence of air, KCN reduces the oxygen uptake, it is of interest to enquire how far the gluconic acid production by the living fungus would also be affected by KCN. The question naturally arises how far this inhibitor affects the gluconic acid fermentation process by the living mould. The glucose medium was prepared with different concentrations of KCN, taken in conical flasks labelled A, B and C and then inoculated with the spores of the strain. Another set of experiments was conducted side by side in flasks D, E and F in which the mycelial mat was grown in a medium prepared without KCN for a few days and then allowed to ferment a fresh solution containing different concentrations of KCN. Growth was observed accompanied by the formation of gluconic acid as shown in Table X.

TABLE X

Name.	Conc. of KCN.	% Yield on glucose taken.	Name.	Conc. of KCN.	% Yield on glucose taken.
A	0.2 mg./c.c.	62.1	D	0.2 mg./c.c.	72.9
B	0.4	50.3	E	0.4	68.1
C	0.8	38.6	F	0.8	57.0

The presence of cyanide did not stop the gluconic acid formation, but only lowered the yield (Table X). This can be readily explained if we assume that of the two factors involved in gluconic acid formation, only one was blocked by cyanide and thereby the yield was lowered, whilst the other functioned normally, unaffected by the presence of cyanide.

Cytochrome Oxidase System.

In order to test whether the cyanide-sensitive part in the glucose oxidation enzyme system is identical with or closely related to the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system, its behaviour towards *p*-phenylene diamine was studied. The results (Table XI) were negative. It appears therefore that this system is absent from the mycelium and consequently the cyanide-sensitive part of the enzyme system concerned in the oxidation of glucose is distinct from the cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system. It is probable that this oxidase is specific for glucose.

TABLE XI

System.	0 min.	20 min.	40 min.	60 min.	80 min.	120 min.
	Oxygen absorption mm. ³ at N.T.P.					
Enzyme alone	0	15	12	22	40	92
<i>p</i> -Phenylens diamine	0	22	39	57	90	186
Boiled enzyme + <i>p</i> -phenylene diamine	0	0	21	29	42	57
Enzyme + <i>p</i> -phenylene diamine	0	9	19	32	47	63

DISCUSSION

The oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid in presence of oxygen by moulds is not due to a common principle; it depends on the nature of the particular strain of the mould concerned. In the particular strain under consideration the properties of the dead mycelium preparation, in relation to its behaviour towards p_{O_2} and temperature and its marked specificity towards glucose, have been studied. The experiments in Warbur's manometer as well as in Thunberg's tube indicate that the oxidation may be due to one component (one component theory) or may be due to two components (two component theory) linked together for the same end. According to the first theory, the oxidation is due to glucose dehydrogenase to which both molecular oxygen and 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol can act as hydrogen acceptor. According to the second theory, the first of the two components is a glucose oxidising system composed of either a specific glucose oxidase (which requires molecular oxygen for its activity) or a non-specific molecular oxygen-activating mechanism like cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase; and the second component is a specific glucose dehydrogenase. In both the theories the existence of a glucose dehydrogenase is assumed, although it has not been possible to identify the product of glucose dehydrogenation as gluconic acid. But there are good reasons to believe that the product of anaerobic dehydrogenation is gluconic acid. Firstly, the anaerobic dehydrogenation of glucose is not inhibited by KCN, as also the certain fraction of aerobic oxidation, which results in the formation of a product, identical with gluconic acid. Secondly, the presence of KCN does not stop the formation of gluconic acid by the living strain of *A. niger*, but only lowers the yield which indicated that the path which was blocked and which was not by KCN led to the formation of gluconic acid. The fact that in our experiments KCN inhibits the oxidation and gluconic acid production not completely but only to a definite degree supports the two component theory. If only one dehydrogenase is involved, as in the one component theory, KCN should not have inhibited the oxidation at all or should have inhibited it completely. If there are two component enzyme systems, one of which is cyanide sensitive and the other cyanide-insensitive, then the partial but definite inhibition of oxidation produced by KCN is readily explained. The behaviour of the living strain towards KCN furnishes another evidence in support of the two component theory. The growth of the strain in presence of air is not inhibited by KCN, but the yield is lowered. This can be readily explained if we assume that of the two independent paths leading to the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid, one viz., the aerobic path i.e., glucose oxidase was blocked, whilst the other is free to act. Consequently the yield is lowered instead of being completely inhibited. During the *in vivo* experiments there was hardly any gluconic acid formation nor any further increase in weight of the mycelium occurred, when the aerobic growth of the strain was incubated anaerobically even in presence of hydrogen acceptors. On the other hand, gluconic acid formation as also increase in weight of mycelium occurred when aerobic growths, after anaerobic incubation, was further incubated in presence of air. Thus the synthesis of cells is accompanied by the formation of gluconic acid.

The nature of the cyanide-sensitive oxidase component involved has been further studied and as it is unable to oxidise *p*-phenylene diamine, this glucose oxidase system appears to be distinct from the non-specific cytochrome-cytochrome oxidase system which readily oxidises *p*-phenylenediamine. In all probability, the oxidase system concerned is specific for glucose.

To summarise the above facts, it may be concluded that the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid is due to both glucose oxidase and glucose dehydrogenase. They can act independently, but their effects are additive.

Glucose + glucose dehydrogenase $\rightarrow$ Gluconic acid

Glucose + glucose oxidase $\rightarrow$ Gluconic acid

Since both the enzymes have nearly the same p_{H} optima, the physiological conditions under which the fermentation process is carried out enable both of them (enzymes) to operate simultaneously for the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid.

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